

The importance of the environment of a small group in promoting dialogical learning and growth in faith of its members: a thematic review of literature.

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Abstract

This paper draws upon a variety of educational and spiritual formational literature to consider several characteristics that encourage dialogical learning among small groups of individuals. The paper is related to a broader research project examining whether participation in small Evangelical church groups helps their members grow in their faith. Studies show that small groups (usually 3-20 people) are widespread in the modern Christian church. They generally meet at a different time than the main weekly church service and offer a place for activities such as prayer, Bible study, the building of community, and outreach.

From April to May 2021, I collected data from three such small groups, each group connected to a different Evangelical congregation in the Republic of Ireland, using in-depth semi-structured interviews (n = 13). This paper presents some of the characteristics I developed in a thematic literature review intended to aid in the practical understanding and analysis of the interview data from these particular small groups. With this focus and based on my literature review, I developed three general themes, each containing various points. This paper briefly outlines some aspects of the first theme developed. The theme relates to the environment small groups can create to promote support and the growth in faith of their membership.

Keywords: dialogical learning, religious education, faith, adult education, COVID, online learning, small groups

Three Key Highlights

- The potential of small groups as a supportive and transformational space for growth in religious faith and adult education is observed.
- The importance of the small group environment to encourage such growth in faith is a recurrent theme in relevant small group literature.
- Three factors that can aid in creating an environment for growth are noted: community, safety, and trust.

Introduction

This paper draws upon a variety of educational and spiritual formational literature to consider several characteristics that encourage dialogical learning among small groups of individuals. It primarily focuses on points I developed in my thematic literature review as part of a larger research project. Thus, a brief review of the larger project is germane to contextualise this literature review.

The broader research project examined whether participation in Evangelical (see Mitchel, 2008; EAI, 2018) church small groups (henceforth SGs) helps their members grow in their faith. Research shows that SGs (usually 3-20 people) are widespread in the modern Christian church (Wuthnow, 1994a; Walton, 2011; Hussey, 2020; Perry, 2021). The potential for SGs to provide a supportive and transformational space for growth has long been recognised both within the religious and educational spheres (Richards, 1975; Harris, 1989; Bielo, 2009; Walton, 2011) and in adult education in general (Vella, 2002). Evidence of their popularity is observed in churches from the Republic of Ireland (henceforth, Ireland). Within the Reformed and Evangelical churches, small groups of various kinds are well established (PCI, 2016; EAI, 2018). Likewise, the Catholic church has also developed a wide variety of such groups (Irish Episcopal Conference, 2010). These SGs generally meet at a different time than the main weekly church service (Astin, 2002) and offer a place for activities such as prayer, Bible study, the building of community, and outreach (Arnold, 2004). From April to May 2021, I collected data from three such small groups, each group connected to a different Evangelical congregation in Ireland, using in-depth semi-structured interviews (n = 13).

Methods

The three SGs chosen all operated during the significant time period of the COVID lockdown restrictions in Ireland. Their meetings were conducted virtually during all the periods considered in this research. The SGs were similar in many other respects. Each group was mixed-gender and part of a larger congregation. They all involved teaching, discussion and some form of prayer ministry in their meetings; however, they varied in how they attended to each element. Finally, they all involved their members in some form of Christian education.

Consequently, the broader research project is situated in adult religious education and formational practices, especially as they relate to the church context. I utilised semi-structured interviews involving several participants from each SG to understand Christian growth through SG participation better. The data for this research was analysed utilising Braun and Clarke's (2021b) six-phase approach to reflexive thematic analysis (RTA). I followed a more inductive approach, 'looking for patterns' that could be 'used to generate theory or explanation' rather than a deductive approach of beginning with a theory or hypothesis (Pope and Mays, 2020, p. 18). RTA's reflexive and fluid nature was helpful as the early creation of a codebook may have forestalled the iterative and inductive approach this new research area required, especially as it involved a new area of enquiry in the geographical context where these groups were set (Terry *et al.* 2017).

With the above overview of the broader research project complete, I again consider this paper's specific and narrower focus: points from my literature review. Braun and Clarke (2021a) note that in thematic analysis (TA), 'the analytic process involves immersion in the data, reading, reflecting, questioning, imagining, wondering, writing, retreating, returning' (2021a, p. 5). Thus my literature review involved many returnings and ongoing conversations with the developing themes from the interview data and the theoretical writings on SGs, as well as my identification of relevant correlations between both. I began a general review of the literature based on my research questions. However, I later reexamined the literature from a thematic perspective, specifically considering themes congruent with areas highlighted by my ongoing analysis of the interview data.

Consequently, my literature review involved the highly interactive process of repeatedly switching between the literature and the phenomenon of interest (Merriam and Tisdell, 2015). The review sought to aid in the practical understanding and analysis of the interview data from the SGs in this particular thesis and not necessarily to predict or generalise theory to all settings (Irby, 1995). With this focus and based on my review of the literature, I developed three general themes. This paper highlights several points from the first theme: *the environment small groups can create to promote the support and growth in faith of their membership*. It is not an exhaustive list, but it highlights some of the findings that were useful for this research project.

Ethical considerations

Ethics involves sensitivity to the risks of human subjects in research. From the outset, I focused on this area by following university procedures for ethical approval. Potential physical and other risks were considered, and minimisation or mitigation procedures were developed. The research itself constituted a low-risk project. Additionally, every participant was an adult able to give informed consent before participating in the research. A plain language statement and consent forms were provided, explaining what was expected from the interviewees before they consented to be involved. If the nature of the subject matter made anyone feel uncomfortable, they could decline consent at the beginning or opt out at any time. Interviews were assigned codes to help prevent participant identification, and participants were referred to using participant codes or pseudonyms.

Results

The importance of the environment for discipleship growth, the potential of SGs to provide this environment, and the promotive conditions are recurrent themes in the relevant literature (Everist, 2002; Hull, 2006; Ogden, 2016). Smaller-sized groups, where relationships can develop, may lead to people sharing their lives more transparently and finding support. This sums up much of the appeal of Christian SGs (Wuthnow, 1994a, 1994b). However, as Richards (1975) observes, ‘while the smaller groupings of believers in the church have the potential of providing a context for transforming ministry, smaller groups will not necessarily have this impact. Size is no guarantee of intimacy or warmth’ (1975, p. 266). Consequently, he warns against ‘a formal, impersonal atmosphere’ and encourages instead intentionally taking the time and effort to develop a ‘warm and sharing climate’, where people feel free to ‘share’ (1975, p. 266). Safety and trust must be present in the SG for such an ideal environment to develop community. These qualities provide part of the foundation for support, sharing, and transformational growth in the lives of SG members.

Community

The deliberate relationship-building or fellowship (Harris, 1989) is seen as providing the context for the deep and meaningful conversations necessary for support. The SG's confidentiality also creates a safe and trusting environment where people feel open to share

their life and can find support in struggles and encouragement in their journey of faith. Astin's (2002) experience of introducing cell meetings (type of SG) into an established Anglican church in Bradford, UK, illustrates this point. Noting how people might say they are fine, whether in reality they were or not, he explains how this was often the experience in his congregation (2002). However, Astin discovered that membership in a cell group provided an environment for deepening friendships and relationships where people became more real as they gradually gained the confidence to speak about how they were coping and feeling about what they faced in their lives (2002).

The growth that takes place in a relational SG environment is also highlighted by Bielo (2009). Bielo's (2009) research on a mixed-gender home group showed that the members not only sought to understand the Bible but demonstrated an attempt to cultivate and increase their intimacy. This overarching relational framework influenced the structure of the meeting, how it operated, the personal prayer opportunities it offered members, and even the approach it took to Bible interpretation (2009, pp. 73–92). The desire for such a close intimate bond with God and fellow church members is thus a notable characteristic among Evangelicals (Bielo, 2009). The intimate spirituality they seek with God is a model for their relationships with one another. As the SG has a reputation in Evangelical life as a place of 'active, open, and reflexive dialogue', it provides an ideal space to cultivate such intimacy (Bielo, 2009, p. 76).

Safety

To facilitate such intimacy, one's 'Christian family is ideally a safe haven, a place to reveal the utmost private triumphs, concerns, and problems without fear of ridicule or exile' (Bielo, 2009, p. 76). A feeling of safety in an environment (Davie, 1995; Everist, 2002; Bielo, 2009; Walton, 2014) is established through slowly building deep trusting relationships (Harris, 1989; Everist, 2002) and is essential in enabling effective support to take place. Nevertheless, what such a safe environment implies for learning can differ and thus requires definition. Everist (2002) acknowledges the strengths and limitations of various words to capture this optimum environment for learning. Safe, or comfortable, may suffer from the drawback of signalling the absence of challenge, acceptance to change, or the misunderstanding that Christians are kept safe from the world and their responsibility to it (Everist, 2002).

For example, in Davie's (1995) study of a women's SG, the safe environment was mediated from the outset through an agreement that everyone was invited to speak but that what was said in the group should remain private and that there should be no fear of ridicule, embarrassment or any sense of competition among group members. It is safe because confrontation is forbidden, and since spiritual growth was envisioned as an individual process, this prohibition even extended to members challenging differences between other members regarding their set of beliefs or views of God (Davie, 1995). Davie judged this privacy as an aspect of the Presbyterian and Protestant culture that this specific group belonged to (1995). That the SG merely provides a safe, non-challenging environment to develop community is emphasised even more forcefully by Wuthnow (1994b). He asserts that while the formal structures of SGs create a space for developing relationships between members, the *raison d'être* of these groups is 'quite often to provide deep, intimate interpersonal support-period' (1994b, p. 159). He views this as a modern redefinition of spirituality and argues that it promotes an unbalanced focus on the individual's comfort and feelings, with the prime goal of helping them get along and be happy over and above focusing on goodness, reverence of God and the type of risk-taking that might be needed for true growth to emerge (Wuthnow, 1993).

However, that safe communication automatically implies the limited and non-challenging approach Davie (1995) reports or that SGs merely involve 'intimate interpersonal support-period' (Wuthnow, 1994b, p. 159) may be minimalistic. Davie (1995) herself, recognised 'participation in a viable spirituality and community' within her research group and that it provided 'emotional and spiritual satisfactions' and created a shared 'bond' in learning together (Davie, 1995, p. 74). Wuthnow (1993) noted that SGs enabled people to cope more effectively with everyday life and acknowledged that they 'sometimes challenge their members to undertake painful processes of spiritual growth', albeit that this pattern is less common in his judgement (Wuthnow, 1993, p. 1240). In line with a broader view, the meaning of the word safe is defined by Everist (2002) as a needed physical and emotional space for openness, honesty, and the probing of new ideas. These results already move beyond the idea of simple interpersonal support or shallow sharing (Everist, 2002). This depth in sharing aligns with Bielo's (2009) judgement of SGs as settings for 'active, open, and reflexive dialogue' (Bielo, 2009, p. 76).

Trust

Everist (2002) further suggests that for some, trustworthy is a better word, as this describes building a SG environment that provides a foundation for security but also for risk-taking. Everest's (2002) broader understanding of safety encompasses a supportive and challenging environment that engenders discipleship growth (see also Vella, 2002, pp. 71–83, contra Wuthnow 1993). Members feel cared for while also hearing and being challenged by the scriptures and one another to 'be equipped to be sent out, to follow Jesus by serving in the world' (Everist, 2002, p. 69).

Thus, building a trusting environment enables members to receive the truth of the scriptures from one another and is, therefore, a prerequisite for learning (Hull, 2006; Ogden, 2016). Hull (2006, p. 154) writes,

The shell-shocked people who ask, "Can I trust me with you?" reveal the most important requirement for spiritual development [...] When you find someone you can trust, then you can be vulnerable. [...] Trust is key, because we only take in the truth we trust. [...] This is where transformational traction takes place.

(2006, p. 156)

Likewise, Ogden (2016) argues that 'a trustworthy environment' promotes 'ever-increasing openness and transparency' in relationships and is a 'key ingredient for continual transformation' (2016, p. 145). His rationale is that while Bible studies are a mainstay in Evangelical churches, they often produce 'limited life transformation' focusing on increasing 'information without life application' (2016, p. 153). Therefore, Ogden (2016) notes,

This is why the atmosphere of transparent trust is so vital if we want God's Word to take root deeply in the soil of our lives. This application of the Word to life is what I call truth in community. We bring our open lives to the Word of God and allow it to do its work in us as we share our stories and journey together.

(2016, p. 153)

Ogden (2016) posits that people are more open to receiving the truth from those they trust, highlighting the importance of trust being developed in the community if the scriptures are to exert their transformative power. Naturally, however, trust requires development, as is seen in Everist's (2002, p. 66) advice for teaching in the church community,

Trust builds slowly, deliberately. One becomes trusted by being consistently trustworthy. [...] when one trusts the learners and gradually helps them trust themselves and each other, individuality flourishes, and, thereby community. [...] Being simplistically trusting, in a shallow, hesitant sense is not helpful. A trustworthy environment provides a foundation for both security and risk-taking.

Ogden (2016) agrees that members need to listen to one another, keep confidences, and be full of grace and humility with one another for an atmosphere of trustworthiness to develop.

Limitations of paper

This paper has outlined several points from the first theme of a thematic literature review. It is not an exhaustive list of this theme. Nevertheless, the paper indicates the broad scope for further fruitful research into the potential SGs may offer as spaces for transformative learning and growth and the importance of developing a healthy environment within such groups.

Conclusions

The importance of the environment for discipleship growth, the potential of SGs to provide this environment, and the promotive conditions in the SGs for growth are recurrent themes in SG literature. This study has highlighted the importance a warm, gracious and affirming atmosphere, where people feel there is a safe and confidential space to share and listen to each other, develop trust and receive input from one another, can have on an individual's growth in faith. However, it emphasises that it is not merely the size of the groups but the development and presence of such qualities in their environment that enable them to impact their members positively. Thus, The study highlights the importance of taking the time necessary to develop such a safe and sharing space in SGs.

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